

Effects of Size, Basicity and Steric Hindrance on the Solution Stability of Binary and Ternary Complexes of Cadmium(II) with some Amino Acids and Formic Acid : A Polarographic Study

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Polarographic technique was used to determine the values of stability constants ($\log \beta$) of binary and ternary complexes of Cd^{II} with L-lysine, L-ornithine, L-threonine, L-serine, L-phenylglycine, L-phenylalanine, L-glutamic acid and L-aspartic acid as primary ligands and formic acid as secondary ligand at $\text{pH} = 8.50$ and ionic strength $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M}$ (KNO_3) at 25° . Cd^{II} forms 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 2 : 1 and 1 : 1 : 2 complexes with selected amino acids and formic acid with stability trend L-lysine < L-ornithine < L-threonine < L-serine < L-phenylglycine < L-phenylalanine < L-glutamic acid < L-aspartic acid, which is explained on the basis of size, basicity and steric hindrance of these ligands

The complexes of amino acids with transition metals are used in biology and as medicines and laboratory reagents¹. In the present study ternary complexes of Cd^{II} with L-lysine, L-ornithine, L-threonine, L-serine, L-phenylglycine, L-phenylalanine, L-glutamic acid and aspartic acid as primary ligands and formic acid as secondary ligand have been reported with the view to ascertain the effect of size, basicity and steric hindrance on the solution stability of the complexes as a part of our programme for which no references could be traced so far in the literature.

Results and Discussion

Cadmium gives a well-defined two-electron reversible reduction wave in KNO_3 ². The plot of $\log(i_a - i)/i$ vs E_{a} gives straight lines with a slope of $30 \pm 1 \text{ mV}$ showing reversible reduction waves of Cd and all its complexes. The i_a vs $\sqrt{h}$ plots are straight lines passing through the origin, confirming the diffusion-controlled nature of the waves.

Binary complexes: The study of binary complexes of Cd^{II} with formic acid at $\text{pH} 8.50 \pm 0.1$ has already been done in our laboratory³. Cd^{II} forms 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with formic acid with stability constant $\log \beta_{01} = 2.26$ and $\log \beta_{02} = 3.80$ respectively.

The pK values of the selected amino acids were determined by titration methods⁴ (Table 1). The free ligand concentrations of amino acids were determined by pK_a^{H} and pH of the test solutions. DeFord and Hume⁵ method revealed the formation of 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes of Cd^{II} with selected amino acids.

The data and plots between $F_1 [X]$ and $[X]$, where $[X]$ = primary ligand (i.e. L-lysine) are given in Table 2 and Fig. 1, respectively. The values of stability constants are given in Table 1.

Ternary complexes: The ternary system, i.e. [Cd-amino acid-formate] was studied by keeping the concentrations of formate ions constant at 0.005 and 0.01 M while varying the concentration of each

TABLE 1— pK VALUES AND STABILITY CONSTANTS* OF BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXES OF Cd^{II} WITH AMINO ACID AND FORMIC ACID

$\mu = 1.0 \text{ M}$, temp. = 25° , $\text{pH} = 8.50 \pm 0.1$

Ligand	pK_a^{H}	$\log \beta_{01}$	$\log \beta_{02}$	$\log \beta_{10}$	$\log \beta_{20}$	$\log \beta_{30}$	$\log \beta_{11}$	$\log \beta_{12}$	$\log \beta_{21}$
L-Lysine	8.95	—	—	3.70	6.48	9.24	5.65	7.57	7.87
L-Ornithine	8.98	—	—	3.77	6.61	9.42	5.81	7.80	8.10
L-Threonine	9.00	—	—	4.00	7.00	9.50	5.96	8.00	8.37
L-Serine	9.20	—	—	4.07	7.13	9.69	6.12	8.22	8.59
L-Phenylglycine	9.23	—	—	4.10	7.24	9.71	6.24	8.40	8.72
L-Phenylalanine	9.30	—	—	4.17	7.37	9.90	6.40	8.62	8.94
L-Glutamic acid	9.67	—	—	4.30	7.45	10.06	6.62	8.82	9.21
L-Aspartic acid	9.82	—	—	4.37	7.58	10.24	6.78	9.10	9.43
Formic acid	—	2.26	3.80	—	—	—	—	—	—

*Original values upto 4th decimal place.

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND $F_1[X]$ VALUES FOR CADMIUM-L-LYSINATE SYSTEM
 ($E_{1/2}$) $M = -0.586$ V vs SCE, $\mu = 1.0$ M (KNO_3), temp = 25°, pH = 8.50 $\pm$ 0.1

Sl no.	$10^3 [L-Lys.]$ M	$\Delta E_{1/2}$ V	$\log I_m/I_c$	$F_0[X]$	$F_1[X]$ $\times 10^{-3}$	$F_2[X]$ $\times 10^{-6}$	$F_3[X]$ $\times 10^{-9}$
1	0.00	—	—	—	—	—	—
2	0.50	0.019	0.007 17	4.46	6.93	3.86	17.39
3	1.00	0.030	0.007 17	10.73	9.73	4.73	17.38
4	2.00	0.046	0.014 4	36.90	17.95	6.47	17.38
5	3.00	0.057	0.021 9	89.54	29.51	8.17	17.24
6	4.00	0.066	0.021 9	180.27	44.81	9.95	17.39
7	5.00	0.073	0.029 4	316.09	63.02	11.60	17.21
8	6.00	0.079	0.029 4	512.20	85.20	13.36	17.28
9	7.00	0.084	0.037 1	757.81	108.11	14.73	16.76
10	8.00	0.089	0.037 1	1 123.29	140.28	16.91	17.39
11	10.00	0.096	0.044 9	2 089.89	208.89	20.39	17.39

$\log \beta_0 = 0.00$, $\log \beta_1 = 3.69$ $\log \beta_2 = 6.47$ $\log \beta_3 = 9.23$

 Fig. 1 Cadmium-L-Lysinate System, $\log \beta_0 = 0.00$, $\log \beta_1 = 3.69$, $\log \beta_2 = 6.47$, $\log \beta_3 = 9.23$ (Δ) $F_0[X]$, ($\bullet$) $F_1[X] \times 10^{-3}$, ($\circ$) $F_2[X] \times 10^{-6}$ and ($\blacktriangle$) $F_3[X] \times 10^{-9}$.

amino acids from 0.5 to 10 mM separately and current-voltage curves were drawn at pH = 8.50 $\pm$ 0.1. The half-wave potential shifted to more negative value in the presence of formate ions than in its absence, showing mixed ligand complex formation. The nature of waves was reversible and diffusion-controlled in each ternary system. Schaap and McMaster⁶ method revealed the formation of 1:1:1, 1:2:1 and 1:1:2 complexes of Cd^{II} with all the selected amino acid and formic acid.

The results⁷ and the plots of $F_i[X, Y]$ vs [L-Lysinate-Formate] are presented in Tables 3 and 4 and Figs. 2 and 3 respectively. The values of stability constants are given in Table 1. The equilibria for the systems are presented in Schemes 1–8 where the numerical values indicate the logarithms of equilibrium constants.

The values of mixing constants ($\log K_m$) used to compare the stability constants of binary and ternary complexes are calculated by the following equation,

$$\log K_m = \log \beta_{11} - 1/2 (\log \beta_{02} + \log \beta_{20})$$

which are 0.511, 0.605, 0.560, 0.655, 0.720, 0.815, 0.995 and 1.09 for [Cd-L-Lys.-For.], [Cd-L-Orn.-For.], [Cd-L-Threo.-For.], [Cd-L-Ser.-For.], [Cd-L-Phenylgly-For.], [Cd-L-Phenylala.-For.], [Cd-L-Glut.-For.], [Cd-L-Asp.-For.] systems respectively, showing that the ternary complexes are more stable than the binary complexes. The sequence of stability with respect to binary and ternary complexes is L-lysine < L-ornithine < L-threonine < L-serine < L-phenylglycine < L-phenylalanine < L-glutamic acid < L-aspartic acid. It has been observed that if the side-chain of amino acid increases, stability of complexes decreases by a constant factor definitively, $\log \beta_{RSB}^*$, i.e. [Cd-(L-Lysinate)]⁺, [Cd-(L-Lysinate)₂] and [Cd-(L-Lysinate)₃]⁻ have lesser stability than [Cd-(L-Ornithinate)₃]⁻ by $\log \beta_{RSB10} = 0.07$, $\log \beta_{RSB20} = 0.13$ and $\log \beta_{RSB30} = 0.19$ respectively; similar effect of side-chain has also been observed in case of other amino acids complexes except in the case of L-phenylglycine and L-phenylalanine where the order was reversed, i.e. L-phenylglycine < L-phenylalanine. This reversal of order of stability might be due to the presence of bulkier group, i.e. phenyl group at β -carbon atom in the case of L-phenylalanine whereas it is at α -carbon atom in the case of L-phenylglycine causing the greater steric hindrance in the later than in the former resulting the lesser stability of L-phenylglycine complexes than L-phenylalanine complexes.

TABLE 3—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND F_{ij} [X, Y] VALUES FOR CADMIUM-L-LYSINATE-FORMATE SYSTEM ($E_{1/2}$)M = -0.586 V vs SCE, μ = 1.0 M (KNO₃), Formate = 0.005 M (fixed), temp. = 25°, pH = 8.50 ± 0.1

Sl. no.	[L-Lys.] × 10 ³ M	$\Delta E_{1/2}$ V	log I_m/I_c	F_{00} [X, Y]	F_{10} [X, Y] × 10 ⁻³	F_{20} [X, Y] × 10 ⁻⁶	F_{30} [X, Y] × 10 ⁻⁹
1.	0.00	—	—	—	—	—	—
2.	0.50	0.020	0.007 17	4 98	5.82	4.29	17.37
3.	1.00	0.030	0.007 17	10.90	8.83	5.16	17.40
4.	2.00	0.046	0.014 4	37.09	17.51	6.92	17.50
5.	3.00	0.057	0.021 9	90.70	29.55	8.62	17.35
6.	4.00	0.066	0.029 4	182.51	45.11	10.36	17.35
7.	5.00	0.073	0.029 4	323.05	64.19	12.10	17.37
8.	6.00	0.079	0.029 4	522.41	86.72	13.84	17.37
9.	7.00	0.084	0.037 1	793.86	113.11	15.63	17.45
10.	8.00	0.089	0.037 1	1 136.03	141.75	17.26	17.30
11.	10.00	0.096	0.044 9	2 117.73	211.57	20.79	17.37

log A = 0.31. log B = 3.57. log C = 6.53. log D = 9.24.

TABLE 4—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND F_{ij} [X, Y] VALUES FOR CADMIUM-L-LYSINATE-FORMATE SYSTEM ($E_{1/2}$)M = -0.586 V vs SCE, μ = 1.0 M (KNO₃), Formate = 0.01 M (fixed), temp. = 25°, pH = 8.50 ± 0.1

Sl. no.	[L-Lys.] × 10 ³ M	$\Delta E_{1/2}$ V	log I_m/I_c	F_{00} [X, Y]	F_{10} [X, Y] × 10 ⁻³	F_{20} [X, Y] × 10 ⁻⁶	F_{30} [X, Y] × 10 ⁻⁹
1.	0.00	—	—	—	—	—	—
2.	0.50	0.030	0.007 17	11.21	15.53	4.61	16.38
3.	1.00	0.039	0.007 17	22.16	18.71	5.50	17.39
4.	2.00	0.052	0.014 4	58.82	27.68	7.23	17.40
5.	3.00	0.061	0.014 4	123.82	40.12	8.96	17.39
6.	4.00	0.069	0.021 9	227.58	56.03	10.70	17.38
7.	5.00	0.075	0.029 4	380.69	75.45	12.44	17.39
8.	6.00	0.081	0.029 4	593.42	98.33	14.18	17.40
9.	7.00	0.686	0.037 1	878.58	124.73	15.92	17.42
10.	8.00	0.090	0.044 9	1 241.41	154.71	17.68	17.42
11.	10.00	0.097	0.052 9	2 249.68	224.62	21.14	17.39

log A = 0.54. log B = 4.12. log C = 6.54. log D = 9.23.

Fig. 2. Cadmium-L-Lysinate-Formate System; log A = 0.31, log B = 3.56, log C = 6.53, log D = 9.23: (Δ) F_{00} [X, Y], ($\bullet$) F_{10} [X, Y] × 10⁻³, ($\circ$) F_{20} [X, Y] × 10⁻⁶ and ($\blacktriangle$) F_{30} [X, Y] × 10⁻⁹.

Fig. 3. Cadmium-L-Lysinate-Formate System; log A = 0.53, log B = 4.12, log C = 6.54, log D = 9.24: (Δ) F_{00} [X, Y], ($\bullet$) F_{10} [X, Y] × 10⁻³, ($\circ$) F_{20} [X, Y] × 10⁻⁶ and ($\blacktriangle$) F_{30} [X, Y] × 10⁻⁹.

Scheme 1. [Cd-L Lysinate-Formate] system.

Scheme 5. [Cd-L-Phenyl-Glycinate-Formate] system.

Scheme 2. [Cd-L-Ornithinate-Formate] system.

Scheme 6. [Cd-L-Phenyl-Alaninate-Formate] system.

Scheme 3. [Cd-L-Threoninate-Formate] system.

Scheme 7. [Cd-L-Glutamate-Formate] system.

Scheme 4. [Cd-L-Serinate-Formate] system.

Scheme 8. [Cd-L-Aspartate-Formate] system.

The stability of L-lysinate complexes is minimum, this is due to the lowest pK values of L-lysine, as pK value increases stability of complexes increases⁹. The lesser stability of L-threoninate complexes than L-serinate is due to the fact that the electron withdrawing OH group is nearer to the metal in the former than in the latter causing greater repulsive forces between OH group and in metal ions in L-threoninate complexes than in L-serinate complexes. The higher stability of L-phenylglycinate complexes than those of L-serinate and L-threoninate complexes can be explained on the basis of hydrogen bond formation between OH and amino group in L-serinate and L-threoninate complexes resulting the lesser stabilities of their complexes than L-phenylalanine and L-phenylglycine. The stability of L-glutamate complexes is lower than L-aspartate complexes which might be a result of ring size, as the L-glutamate formed five- and seven-membered rings whereas L-aspartate made five- and six-membered rings in complex formation. As the ring size increases the stability of complex decrease⁹. The stabilities of the L-glutamate and L-aspartate complexes are greater than those of the L-lysinate, L-ornithinate, L-threoninate, L-serinate, L-phenylglycinate, L-phenylalaninate complexes as a results of large differences in their basic strengths.

For ternary complexes, the stabilities of [Cd-Lys.-For.], [Cd-(L-Lys.)₂-For.]⁻ and [Cd-(L-Lys).(For.)₂]⁻ are lower than [Cd-(L-Orn.)-For.], [Cd-(L-Orn.)₂-For.]⁻, [Cd-(L-Orn.)-(For.)₂]⁻ by constant factors log β_{RST}[†], i.e. log β_{RST,11} = 0.16, log β_{RST,21} = 0.22, and log β_{RST,12} = 0.22 respectively. This is true for all the complexes from [L-Lys.-For.] complexes to [L-Asp.-For.] complexes except in the [L-Phenylgly.-For.] and [L-Phenylala.-For.] complexes, where the order was reversed. The factors log β_{RST}[†] and log β_{RST}[‡] are given by the equation⁹,

$$\log \beta_{RST}^{\ddagger} = \frac{(Z+4)im}{12(Z+5)}$$

$$\log \beta_{RST}^{\dagger} = \frac{(Z+4)(i+j)m}{10(Z+5)}$$

where Z represents the charge on the complex, and i, j and m are the stoichiometric numbers for primary ligand, secondary ligand and metal ion respectively, representing the complexation equilibria.

log β_{RST}[‡] and log β_{RST}[†] are the reduction factors diminish the stabilities of binary and ternary complexes when the side-chain in amino acid is increased by CH₂.

The sequence of stabilities of ternary complexes is the same as binary complexes, can also be explained on the basis of size, basicities and steric hindrance of amino acids⁹.

Experimental

A.R. grade chemicals were used to prepare all the solutions in conductivity water. The purity of amino acids were checked by chromatographic method¹⁰. The concentrations of metal, KNO₃ and gelatin in the test solution were 1.0 mM, 1.0 M and 0.001%, respectively.

The depolariser and ligand (i.e. amino acid and formic acid) were taken in the ratio 1 : 40 in case of binary complexes and 1 : 40 : 40 in the case of ternary complexes, and current voltage curves were drawn in each case. Maximum shifts of E_{1/2} was observed at pH = 8.50 ± 0.1, therefore, this pH was selected for the present study.

A manual polarograph using a Toshniwal PL-50 polyflex galvanometer was used to record the current voltage data. The characteristics of capillary were m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.40 mg^{2/3} s^{-1/6} at 60.02 cm (calculated) effective height of mercury². Pure nitrogen gas was passed through each test solution before recording the current-voltage data. The pH of the test solution was measured on a Elico LI-10 pH meter at 8.50 ± 0.1 adjusted with dilute solutions of NaOH or HNO₃ as required. The entire study was carried out at 25°.

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